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Interactive and Collaborative Pedagogical Strategies for Teaching Mathematics at Primary Level: Comparing the Single National Curriculum (2020) and National Curriculum (2006)

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study investigates the pedagogical approach of teaching mathematics at the primary level (grade 5) in the National Curriculum (NC) 2006 and Single National Curriculum (SNC) 2020. The curriculum documents and mathematics textbooks of the two curricula were selected through purposive sampling. The methods used in the evaluation were qualitative content analysis and comparative analysis to determine the presence of pedagogical strategies in the curriculum documents and textbooks and the implementation of these strategies. The results indicate that the SNC 2020 covers a wider range of pedagogical strategies and has a higher level of consistency than the NC 2006. The SNC document had 11 strategies that were specifically stated, compared with the 2006 NC document, which had only six strategies. Likewise, the mathematics textbook of the SNC 2020 has eight strategies, compared to four for the NC 2006 textbook. In general, the SNC 2020 emphasizes inquiry, problem solving, cooperative learning, math lab activities, and activity-based techniques that promote conceptual learning, critical thinking and mathematical reasoning. The study notes that the SNC 2020 has undergone a distinct pedagogical change where mathematics instruction has become more activity-based and learner-focused, which follows the requirements of 21st century skills and facilitates meaningful interaction between students of primary level.

Keywords: Interactive, Collaborative, Pedagogical Strategies, Mathematics Education, Primary level, Single National Curriculum, National Curriculum

Introduction:

Education is the most integral part of individual personality and intellectual growth and plays an important role in the nation-building process. It has been one of the most important goals of various civilizations since ancient times, as a means of transmitting knowledge, skills and cultural values from generation to generation. Education is not just meant to make people smart but also to help them develop moral and ethical values that can make a positive impact on society. Education is not only a process of transferring knowledge, it is also associated with critical thinking, problem solving and adaptability to rapid change (Khaengkhan et al., 2025; Sriatun et al., 2024). Nelson Mandela said, "Education is the most potent weapon which you can use to change the world", in reference to the importance of education.

Building on this foundation, curriculum forms an important part of education. It is a road map for educational programs, which includes curricular and co-curricular programs (Stone & Nelson, 2021). Effective teaching strategies which are applied to deliver this curriculum are what is known as pedagogical strategies and are as important as the curriculum itself. Flexibility, creativity, and the ability to create a learning environment that suits the needs of individual learners are all important components of effective teaching. To effect an essential change in the learner is the main goal of teaching at any level of education. Therefore, teachers need to apply some teaching strategies according to certain objectives and competences to ensure and improve the process of transmitting knowledge (Yelfianita et al., 2023).

Mathematics is an important part of our lives. Learning mathematics helps students think analytically and develop critical thinking skills. It helps them develop the lifelong learning skills needed to solve lifelong problems. Therefore, effective pedagogical strategies play a vital role in transforming students' learning into the classroom by making mathematical concepts more accessible, interesting, and approachable (Mustafa, 2023). Mathematics is a crucial subject that enables students

to develop critical skills, such as logical thinking, reasoning, and problem solving. These skills are especially important at the primary level, where students begin constructing their academic foundations. In the past decades, many educators have widely applied teacher-centred strategies to impart knowledge to learners compared to student-centred strategies (Marinko et al., 2016). Traditional pedagogy methods are teacher-centred, in which students are more passive participants in the learning process. Teachers have relied on teacher-centred approaches for decades. In such methods, students are passive, listening to their teachers, making their notes, engaging in brief discussions with memorizing the facts to be examined. It emphasized knowledge transmission and improved grades rather than training the necessary skills (Tebabal & Kahssay, 2011).

Interactive and collaborative strategies, such as group work, peer dialogue, and hands-on activities have been demonstrated to improve students' knowledge and make learning more significant and engaging. Such strategies encourage students to actively participate in their learning and collaborate to solve problems and complete their tasks. Interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies involve engaging students in meaningful tasks that encourage active participation and cooperation in various roles (Zitha et al., 2023). These pedagogical strategies aim to foster group-based learning and capitalize on the social aspects of education.

In Pakistan, several reforms have been introduced to improve the quality and equity of education in the country. The National Curriculum of 2006 introduced activity-based learning and emphasized concept development. However, it encounters difficulty in its implementation in different parts of the world (Siddiqui et al., 2015). In the view of Article 25-A of the Constitution of Pakistan, free and compulsory education is given to children between the ages of 5 and 16. To fill up these gaps, the government was implementing the Single National Curriculum (SNC 2020) in the vision of one nation, one curriculum.

This study aimed to explore and compare the pedagogical strategies for teaching mathematics at primary level (grade 5) as presented in both the National Curriculum (2006) and the Single National Curriculum (2020). This study aims to analyze how interactive and collaborative strategies are integrated into the curriculum documents and textbooks developed by the Punjab Curriculum and Textbook Board (PCTB) based on the two curriculum frameworks.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To explore and compare the interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies for teaching mathematics at primary level (Grade 5), as mentioned in the National Curriculum (2006) and Single National Curriculum (2020).
2. To analyze the interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies for teaching mathematics at the primary level (Grade 5), as represented in the mathematics textbooks based on the National Curriculum (2006) and the Single National Curriculum (2020).
3. To Compare the National Curriculum (2006) and Single National Curriculum (2022)

Literature Review:

Pedagogy is a broad foundational concept in education. Pedagogy is a contentious concept, yet it refers to actions used to influence student behaviour. According to Bernstein (2000b), pedagogy is "an ongoing process in which someone acquire new

behaviors or expand existing behaviors, knowledge, practices, and criteria with the help of someone or something who are considered appropriate providers and evaluators (Bernstein, 2000a). In modern education, pedagogy has shifted from traditional teacher-centred instruction to more student-centred approaches that foster critical thinking, exploration and problem-solving.

Critical thinking has been the focus of different studies in the Pakistani context regarding teachers, education policy documents and textbooks perspectives (Afriansyah et al., 2021; Ahdhianto et al., 2020; Jamil, 2021; Jamil et al., 2024; Jamil et al., 2021a, 2021b; Naseer et al., 2022).

Pedagogical strategies are intentional and planned approaches used by educators to develop a competent learning environment, including a wide range of procedures utilized to enrich instruction and understanding. They are mainly aimed at actively involving learners, increasing their knowledge, and eventually achieving high academic achievements (Salamanti et al., 2023).

Pedagogical strategies are essential in effective teaching (Zama & Endeley, 2023). They are a key element that involves placing learners in the learning experience, assisting the understanding of complex concepts, enhancing learning performance to high retention levels and academic achievements, adopting the continuous assessment method to gauge student development, using educational technology, ensuring teacher competence, fostering effective teacher-student interaction, promoting critical thinking in learning through problem-based learning, and personalizing the learning experience to address the needs of individual students. These strategies play significant roles in the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process (Munna & Kalam, 2021) because they define the ways in which knowledge is passed, the ways in which the learners engage with the learning content, and the ways in which the learning results are achieved.

Teaching mathematics at primary level has an important role in developing logical, problem-solving, and analytical thoughts among the students (Lovianova et al., 2022). At this level students are introduced to basic mathematical concepts such as numbers, operations, shapes, measurements, and patterns that are the foundation for learning to come. An information and technology-based society needs people who can think critically about complex issues, analyze and adapt to new situations, solve a variety of problems, and express their opinions effectively. Interactive and collaborative strategies, including the implementation of practical activities, group problem-solving, and peer discussions, may raise students' interest, participation, and comprehension (Alsmadi et al., 2023). These approaches facilitate more comprehensive conceptual knowledge and stimulate students to investigate, discuss, and share mathematical thinking, that is a fundamental element in constructing a sturdy foundation in the field.

Today, teachers need to educate not only to cater to individual learners' needs but also to prepare them for life in a constantly changing global society. The 21st century learning skills are commonly referred to as the 4 Cs: critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and communication. These are the four required skills to prepare learners for the global society. The 21st century skills imply that it is a whole of behavioural training, knowledge and skills which are required to ensure success by teachers, reformers, political leaders and peers in today's global society (Díaz et al., 2022). To develop these 21st century skills, the use of effective pedagogical strategies is crucial as it offers methods and approaches according to which learners may actively develop critical thinking, collaboration, creativity and communication. The importance of interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies in mathematics is particularly

significant because it involves the students in the learning process directly and makes them collaborate to solve problems and build knowledge (Boye & Agyei, 2023). Both of these strategies enhance critical thinking, communication, teamwork, and creativity in order to make the learning process more meaningful and responsive to the needs of the 21st century. Accordingly, there is need to focus on interactive and collaborative pedagogy as this directly contributes to the training of 21st century competencies in the teaching learning process (Peña-Ayala, 2021).

The Single National Mathematics Curriculum 2020 was developed keeping in mind the modern trends in mathematics and the emerging social requirements on the integrity and social cohesion of the country. The main aim of the Single National Mathematics Curriculum 2020 was to develop the sense of mathematical literacy, induce in logical thinking, reasoning, and solve real-life situations among the students. It provides a framework for teachers that is effective and can be used to design and deliver meaningful learning experiences and evaluate them effectively. In addition to knowledge and skills, values are also highlighted within the curriculum to enable the students to develop in their spiritual, moral, social and cultural life through the study of mathematics. The Single National Curriculum is focused on different teaching and learning strategies, as a way of making learning interesting and inclusive. The strategies are well-planned to address the interests, abilities, and learning styles of students to enable them to become independent and confident learners. Researchers have analyzed these strategies qualitatively, based on their key features, purposes, and potential benefits

Research Methodology:

This research adopted qualitative exploratory design, alongside qualitative content analysis and comparative analysis, to study how interactive and collaborative teaching strategies are used in teaching mathematics at the primary level (Grade 5). This study focused on two main curriculum frameworks: The Single National Curriculum (SNC 2020) and the National Curriculum Framework (NC 2006). It also examined the Grade 5 Mathematics textbooks based on these two curricula. The purposive sampling technique was used to select these documents i.e. Single National Curriculum and National Curriculum with Mathematics textbooks.

Findings of the Study

The researchers examined interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies from NC 2006 and SNC 2020. The table was created to show comparative analysis of the pedagogical strategies of each document. We selected 16 instructional practices from Curriculum documents. Second, the Mathematics class 5 textbooks based on NC 2006 and SNC 2020 were carefully examined. The tables were analyzed extensively.

National Curriculum Framework, 2006

The findings of this research suggest pedagogical strategies such as problem solving, mathematics investigation, consolidation and practice, games, practical work, problems, and puzzles. The researchers found that there was less focus on pedagogical strategies in the National Curriculum 2006.

Single National Curriculum Document (2020)

The researchers explored various pedagogical strategies in the SNC (2020) documents, including enquiry-based learning, brainstorming, cooperative learning, demonstration, practical work, math-lab, problem solving, discovery, games, quizzes, and puzzles.

These strategies aim to increase students' active participation in the educational process and the development of their critical thinking, exploration, collaboration, and experiential learning. Such strategies seek to make learning more active so learners can explore ideas, engage in peer-to-peer communication, and practically implement theoretical knowledge in real-life situations.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Pedagogical Strategies in Mathematics Curriculum Documents (NC 2006 and SNC 2020):

Pedagogical Strategies of NC 2006	Pedagogical Strategies of SNC 2020	Comparative Analysis
<p>Investigation Mathematics: Students explore independently, providing opportunities to choose starting points, identifying problems, selecting materials, and presenting solutions</p>	<p>Inquiry based learning: use of questions, problem-solving activities, and real-life scenarios; students investigate and share ideas; teachers facilitate rather than dictates.</p>	<p>Present in both; SNC emphasizes structured, inquiry-based learning with teacher facilitation, while NC promotes independent exploration.</p>
<p>X</p>	<p>Demonstration Approach: Teacher demonstrates concepts, asks questions, and involves learners in reflection and explanation. Learners actively show their understanding and share ideas.</p>	<p>Present in SNC; It helps to make abstract concepts concrete through teacher demonstration and student reflection. But absent in NC</p>
<p>Problem Solving Strategy: Central focus of mathematics, students to think systematically, explore possibilities, and analyze their ideas before coming to a solution.</p>	<p>Problem-Solving Approach Strategy: It involves Step-by-step process involving problem definition, data collection, solution formulation, testing, and conclusion.</p>	<p>Present in both; SNC gives step-by-step structured application, NC focuses more on general problem analysis and verification.</p>
<p>X</p>	<p>Math-Lab Strategy: Encourage students to solve problem in Group work, hands-on activities, freedom to choose materials and methods, teacher acts as guide</p>	<p>Present in SNC; promotes group work, hands-on learning, and real-life applications. But absent in NC.</p>
<p>Games: Mentioned as supportive activity to engage students in practice.</p>	<p>Games: Integrated as interactive tools to enhance engagement, motivation, and conceptual understanding.</p>	<p>Present in both, but SNC gives stronger emphasis on games as formalized strategy for active learning.</p>
	<p>Discovery Approach: To</p>	<p>Highlighted in SNC,</p>

x	develop higher-order thinking skills and encourage students to develop new knowledge from previous knowledge.	focusing on inductive reasoning and higher-order thinking. Absent in NC.
Practical Work Strategy: Students engage in concrete activities occasionally to understand concepts	Practical work: Learning through the use of concrete materials, outdoor and indoor activities, observation and experimentation.	Present in both, but SNC gives stronger focus , emphasizing real-world connections and continuous use of practical work.
x	Cooperative Learning: Formal small-group work, peer support, shared goals, and social interaction.	Present in SNC; focuses on peer learning, teamwork, and collaboration.
x	Brainstorming: the ability to identify, conceptualize, evaluate and execute accordingly; teacher acts as facilitator and records all responses; all suggestions are welcomed without judgment.	Present in SNC; fosters creativity and idea generation, absent in NC.
Consolidation & Practice: Strongly emphasized: drill, repetition, practice exercises for skill mastery.	x	Included in NC; focuses on reinforcement of concepts through practice, not explicitly emphasized in SNC.
Problems & Puzzles: Mentioned as enrichment activities for advanced learners; focus on logical reasoning.	x	Present in NC; reflects its focus on challenging advanced learners

The comparative analysis of pedagogical strategies between NC 2006 and SNC 2020 shows that both curricula have certain common strategies, but the SNC 2020 is more modern, interactive, and student oriented.

Analysis of Class 5 Mathematics Textbooks (NC 2006 and SNC 2020)

Table: 2 (Analysis of Pedagogical Strategies for Teaching Mathematics in Textbooks (Class 5))

Sr #	Pedagogical Strategies	NC 2006	SNC 2020
1	Inquiry Based Learning		✓
2	Brainstorming		

3	Cooperative learning		✓
4	Demonstration		✓
5	Practical Work	✓	✓
6	Math-Lab		✓
7	Problem Solving	✓	✓
8	Discovery		✓
9	Games		
10	Consolidation & Practice	✓	✓
11	Problems & Puzzles		
12	Investigation Mathematics	✓	

The above table shows the 12 pedagogical strategies that are mostly used for teaching mathematics. Of these, according to the researcher, nine strategies were found to be used in the textbook, in different activities, and in several parts of the unit and exercise.

Comparison between NC 2006 and SNC 2020

Table: 3: Comparative Analysis of NC 2006 & SNC 2020

Pedagogical Strategies across both curricula	NC 2006		SNC 2020	
	Curriculum Document	Textbook	Curriculum Document	Textbook
Inquiry Based Learning	X	X	✓	✓
Brainstorming	X	X	✓	X
Cooperative learning	X	X	✓	✓
Demonstration	X	X	✓	✓
Practical Work	X	✓	✓	✓
Math-Lab	X	X	✓	✓
Problem Solving	✓	✓	✓	✓
Discovery	X	X	✓	X
Games	✓	X	✓	X
Consolidation & Practice	✓	✓	X	✓

Above table presents a comparison of NC 2006 and SNC 2020, examining two

Investigation Mathematics	✓	✗	✗	✗
Problems & Puzzles	✓	✗	✗	✗

components of each curriculum: **curriculum documents and textbooks**. According to the table, SNC 2020 includes a broader scope of interactive and collaborative strategies across its documents, including textbooks, compared to NC 2006. Enquiry-based learning, cooperative learning, demonstration, practical work, math-lab activities, games, and problem-solving are more regularly found in the SNC 2020, indicating a stronger emphasis on activity-based and student-centred learning. In contrast, **NC 2006 showed limited integration of most interactive strategies**, with many marked as absent in textbooks. However, NC 2006 includes discovery learning, problem solving, and investigation mathematics at the primary level. Overall, the table shows that the SNC 2020 offers a more consistent and holistic application of pedagogical strategies, which guarantees the consistency of policy documents, learning outcomes, and textbook representations. While conceptually acknowledging certain strategies, the NC 2006 demonstrates limited practical integration across its instructional components.

Discussions

Mathematics education in the curriculum but particularly at the primary level is aimed at developing basic skills such as number sense, computation, measurement and patterns and problem solving. This study discussed the NC 2006 and SNC 2020 as a tool to promote the interactive and collaborative pedagogical approaches of teaching mathematics at the primary school level in Pakistan. Although the SNC 2020 wants to aim at a comprehensive and standardized approach, it does not completely describe strategies for implementation in the classroom but encourages 11 interactive strategies that include group work, problem solving, inquiry, demonstrations and mathematics laboratory investigations. Even though the SNC 2020 was initially envisaged to be implemented at all levels of schooling, its implementation has been delayed by administrative and political delays. In comparison, the NC 2006 still depends on traditional, more teacher-centred approaches and provides less structured options for engaging with students, although problem-solving and investigative tasks are occasionally mentioned.

The literature suggests that two curricula can benefit further from expanding interactive pedagogical strategies to strengthen mathematics instruction. The integration of digital tools, practical resources, math-lab activities, and group learning tasks enriches learning spaces, with students actively exploring concepts, applying mathematical thoughts, and expressing their ideas (Alali & Wardat, 2024; Yadav, 2022). Empirical research has repeatedly shown that students who are given access to interactive, real-life mathematical tools are more driven, more engaged, and have a better grasp of the concepts taught (Mierluş-Mazilu & Yilmaz, 2023; Nilimaa, 2023; Sujatha & Vinayakan, 2023) to them as opposed to students taught using only textbook material or only lecture-based curriculum.

Conclusion

In the present study, the interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies incorporated in the National Curriculum (2006) and the Single National Curriculum (2020) were examined and compared for teaching mathematics at the primary level. A comparison of curriculum documents and Class 5 math textbooks demonstrated apparent differences in the pedagogical orientations used in the two curricula. Although

NC 2006 includes some student-oriented approaches such as problem-solving tasks, investigative mathematics, practical activities, and quizzes, its general focus is still mostly traditional and teacher-centred, thus providing few chances to have a strong student engagement. In addition, the strategies are not consistently reflected in the textbooks. Conversely, the SNC 2020 is more innovative and modern in terms of its pedagogical strategies. It has integrated a wider range of interactive and cooperative strategies that include enquiry-based learning, cooperative learning modules, demonstrative practical work, math-lab activities, educational games, and systematic problem-solving strategies. Such strategies are consistently presented in curriculum documents and textbooks, indicating a stronger alignment between policy and instructional practice. Overall, the research concludes that the SNC can serve to support conceptual knowledge, mathematical thinking, and collaboration between students at the primary level and provide a more holistic approach.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Teachers should receive ongoing and systematic training on interactive and collaborative pedagogical strategies that include enquiry-based learning, cooperative work, demonstration, math-laboratory work, and structured problem-solving to build their confidence and capacity to implement student-centred instruction.
- Digital tools, virtual manipulatives, interactive applications, and mathematics software should be used in classroom teaching.
- Education departments, curriculum, and school leadership should constantly check the application of pedagogical strategies in classrooms.

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